

spectrophotometer. The range covered the ultraviolet (UV), visible, and near-infrared spectrum. The transmittance of whole wavelength range was lowest in both white and brown bread paper bags.

Reduced UV and visible radiation transmittance through the bread paper

bags may minimize photoreceptor activation in the seeds and divert some of the storage carbohydrate to the shikimic process. This would result in heavier seeds for the bread paper-covered panicles than for the glassine-covered panicles □

Effect of type of paper bag used to cover hand-crossed panicles on percentage of seed setting, weight of F₁ seed, seed germination, and hybrid vigor components.^a MORIF, Ujung Pandang, Indonesia, 1991.

Bags used	Seed set percentage (%)	100-seed wt (g)	Seed germination (%)	Seedling plant ht (cm)	Root length (cm)	Dry matter of seedlings (g/5 plants)	Light transmittance (%)	
							250 nm	850 nm
White glassine	24.01	1.5409 c	65.50 b	29.30 b	14.50 bc	0.7103 bc	5.7	23.5
Yellow glassine	32.33	1.3988 c	57.00 bc	29.23 bc	14.67 bc	0.6474 cd	6.0	27.2
Green glassine	27.10	1.5290 c	47.50 cd	26.37 c	13.75 c	0.6961 bcd	0.8	14.2
Red glassine	29.12	1.5151 c	40.25 d	23.47 c	13.92 c	0.6307 d	3.0	38.8
White bread paper	29.83	1.9846 b	64.50 b	30.03 b	15.25 b	0.7598 b	0.6	1.2
Brown bread paper	27.20	2.2427 a	82.00 a	37.33 a	20.75 a	1.0467 d	0.1	3.4
CV (%)	12.5	12.6	10.8	14.2	16.2	11.6		

^a In each column, treatment means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at P = 0.05.

Performance of IRRI rice hybrids in Mandya, Karnataka, India

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Six hybrids using CMS lines IR62829 A and IR58025 A were evaluated against local checks Jaya, IR36, and Rasi at the Regional Research Station, Mandya. Seedlings (26 d old) were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing on 4 Aug 1990 in

5.9-m² plots laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

The IR58025 A combinations outperformed the IR62829 A hybrids and local checks (see table). Jaya yielded more than the IR62829 A hybrids.

IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R matured in 117 d and IR58025 A/IR35366-62-1-2-3 R in 124 d. These hybrids had 25% more standard heterosis than IR36, the comparable check, for days to maturity, and 10% more than Jaya. IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3 R recorded higher yield, but duration was 136 d. □

Performance of IRRI hybrids in Mandya, Karnataka, India.

Hybrid and check	Maturity duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Sterile plants (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) in heterosis over		
								Jaya	IR36	Rasi
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	117	78.2	318	141	10.9	3.9	7.6	10.6	26.2	24.4
IR62829 A/IR9761-19-1 R	120	70.2	428	125	18.2	5.0	4.7	-31.9	-22.3	-23.5
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3 R	136	88.7	422	143	20.4	0	7.6	10.6	26.2	24.4
IR62829 A/IR29723-143-3 R	126	73.9	317	162	36.3	6.2	6.2	-9.0	3.4	-2.3
IR62829 A/IR10198-66-2 R	120	78.6	361	137	5.9	7.6	6.5	-4.9	-8.5	-6.9
IR58025 A/IR35366-62-1-2-3 R	124	80.4	407	172	33.9	6.1	7.7	12.7	28.5	26.7
Jaya	141	100.8	336	155	19.6	0	6.8			
IR36	127	68.4	339	125	20.5	0	6.0			
Rasi	124	85.6	348	127	4.3	0	6.0			
LSD										1.4
CV (%)										13.1

Grain quality

Effect of growth location on rice protein content and composition

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Grain samples of rice cultivar L202 from different locations had varied cooking quality. We studied the effect of growth location on the stability of rice protein content and composition.

L202 seeds from the 1989 harvests in California, USA, and Seville, Spain, were grown in 1990 in Italy.

The protein content of brown rice from Italian crops was lower than that of American and Spanish samples (see table). Quantitative and qualitative differences existed among the four

AL-PAGE patterns of acetic extracts of brown rice from rice cultivar L202 grown in different locations: I = California (Californian seed), II = Italy (Californian seed), III = Spain (Spanish seed), and IV = Italy (Spanish seed).

Effect of growth location on protein content of rice cultivar L202.

Sample	% N × 5.95 ^a
California (California seed)	9.4 a
Italy (California seed)	7.4 d
Spain (Spanish seed)	7.9 b
Italy (Spanish seed)	7.6 c

^a Values with different letters are statistically different at P < 0.05.

samples when acetic acid extracts were analyzed by aluminum lactate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (AL-PAGE) in 10% acrylamide gel.

Overall band intensity of the Italian samples (lanes II and IV in figure) was weaker than that of American and Spanish samples (lanes I and III). Patterns of Italian samples lacked one prominent band (a in figure). The patterns

of the American and Spanish samples were nearly the same; those of the Italian samples were identical.

Differences in the electrophoregrams may be related to the differences in cooking quality. Samples of a cultivar from different agroclimatic regions should be treated separately to maintain the uniqueness of a particular germplasm and/or quality characteristics. □

Milling recovery as influenced by different types of rice mills

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Machinery in milling affects the outturn of head rice and total rice. Using outmoded mills results in relatively higher quantitative and qualitative losses.

We compared different types of rice mills—stedhuller (Engelberg type), disc sheller (under-runner type), and modern rubber roller mill—to assess quantitative losses. Test varieties were KS282 (medium grain) and Basmati 385 (fine grain).

Effect of rice mills on milling recovery.^a

Mill type	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Broken rice (%)
<i>KS282</i>			
Steel huller	67.6 c	51.8 c	15.8 c
Disc sheller	70.0 b	56.2 b	13.8 b
Modern rubber roller	71.7 a	59.6 a	12.1 a
<i>Basmati 385</i>			
Steel huller	66.3 c	49.7 c	16.6 c
Disc sheller	69.0 b	54.0 b	15.0 b
Modern rubber roller	70.0 a	57.0 a	13.5 a

^a On a rough rice basis. Values with different letters are statistically different at P < 0.05 by DMRT.

The modern mill produced more head rice in the test varieties than did either the disc sheller or the steel huller (see table). Total milled rice percentage was also

higher with the modern mill. Different mills produced broken rice ranging from 12.1 to 15.8% for KS282 and 13.5 to 16.6% for Basmati 385. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Inheritance of resistance to rice stripe virus (RSV) in Yunnan Province, China

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We studied the inheritance of resistance to RSV in resistant foreign varieties Zhongguo 91, Fengfeng, and Tetep and native Chinese varieties Shuangfeng 1, Huxuan 19, and 683 Nuo.

Crosses were made in the fall of 1987. Parents, F₁, and F₂ were inoculated at the three-leaf stage with viruliferous small brown planthoppers during summer 1988.

Diseased plants and heart-withered shoots were counted after 25 d. Disease-free seedlings were planted in a field of a heavily diseased district,

Results at seedling and tillering stages were analyzed using a disease index where 0-29% was considered

resistant (R), 30-59% was moderately resistant (MR), and more than 60% was infected (S).

Zhongguo 91, Fengfeng, and Tetep were highly resistant to RSV; Huxuan 19, Shuangfeng 1, and 683 Nuo were moderately resistant. Resistance was

Table 1. Resistance to RSV of parents and F₁. Yunnan Province, China, 1988.

Parents and F ₁	Plants (no.)	Disease incidence (%)	Disease index (%)	Resistance
Zhongguo 91	174	6.9	6.1	R
Huxuan 19	182	40.1	31.9	MR
Shuangfeng 1	60	58.3	51.3	MR
Fengfeng	220	18.6	16.1	R
683 Nuo	190	56.8	48.0	MR
Tetep	96	14.6	10.8	R
Zhongguo 91/Huxuan 19	11	9.1	9.1	R
Huxuan 19/Zhongguo 91	18	5.6	5.6	R
Zhongguo 91/Shuangfeng 1	10	30.0	26.7	R
683 Nuo/Fengfeng	10	20.0	10.0	R
Huxuan 19/Fengfeng	19	26.3	26.3	R
Shuangfeng 1/Tetep	19	21.1	20.2	R